

**International Journal on Integrating Technology in Education
(IJITE)**

ISSN : 2320 - 1886(Online; 2320 - 3935(Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijite/home.html>

**Current Issue : March 2019, Volume 8, Number 1---
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SCHOOL MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS: CHALLENGES TO EDUCATIONAL DECISION-MAKING IN THE BIG DATA ERA

Vivienne V. Forrester
Nova Southeastern University, USA

ABSTRACT

Despite the benefits of school management information systems (SMIS), the concept of data-driven school culture failed to materialize for many educational institutions. Challenges posed by the quality of data in the big data era have prevented many schools from realizing the real potential of the SMIS. The paper analyses the uses, features, and inhibiting factors of SMIS. The paper proposes a five-phase conceptual model that assist administrators with making timely, quality decisions. The paper enriches the theoretical landscape of SMIS usage in the era of big data and lays a foundation for the future by establishing an educational decision-making model.

KEYWORDS

School management information system, big data, educational decision-making, data-driven schools, educational model, student-information system.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijite/V8N1/8119ijite01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/ijite/vol8.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Hinze-Pifer, Rebecca & Daniel S. Ramsey, (2011) "[Evaluating Education Information Systems: Implementation of Longitudinal Student Data Systems in Six School Districts.](#)" Policy Perspectives, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp71-91.
- [2] Wiseman, Alexander W., and Petrina M. Davidson, (2018) "[The Rhythmic Application of EvidenceBased Policy in National Educational Systems Worldwide.](#)" In Cross-nationally Comparative, Evidence-based Educational Policymaking and Reform, pp1-17. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- [3] Carnoy, Martin. (2004) "[ICT in education: Possibilities and challenges.](#)" Inaugural lecture of the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC) 2004–2005 Academic Year, Barcelona.
- [4] Means, Barbara, Christine Padilla, Angela DeBarger, & Marianne Bakia, (2009) "[Implementing DataInformed Decision Making in Schools: Teacher Access, Supports and Use.](#)" US Department of Education.
- [5] Cai, Li, & Yangyong Zhu, (2015). "[The challenges of data quality and data quality assessment in the big data era.](#)" Data Science Journal, Vol.14.
- [6] Laudon, Kenneth C., & Jane P. Laudon, (2015). Management Information Systems: Managing the Digital Firm Plus MyMISLab with Pearson eText--Access Card Package. Prentice Hall Press.
- [7] Moshe, Telem, (1999) "[A case study of the impact of school administration computerization on the department head's role.](#)" Journal of Research on Computing in Education, Vol. 31, No. 4, pp385-401.
- [8] New, Joshua, (2016) "[Building a data-driven education system in the United States.](#)" Center for Data Innovation
- [9] McCrummen, Stephanie, (2010). "D.C. principal's hands-on tack transforms Sousa Middle but also ruffles feathers." Washington Post, June 7.
- [10] Shah, Madiha, (2014) "[Impact of management information systems \(MIS\) on school administration: What the literature says.](#)" Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences, Vol. 116, pp2799-2804.
- [11] Katal, Avita, Mohammad Wazid, & R. H. Goudar, (2013) "[Big data: issues, challenges, tools and good practices.](#)" In 2013 Sixth international conference on contemporary computing (IC3), pp404-409. IEEE.
- [12] Gurr, D, (2000) "The impact of information and communication technology on the work of school principals." Leading & Managing, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp60-73.
- [13] Zavadsky, Heather, (2009) "Building data-driven district systems." Handbook of data-based decision making in education, pp173-190.
- [14] Bernhardt, Victoria L, (2005) "[Data tools for school improvement.](#)" Educational Leadership Vol. 62, No. 5 pp66-69.

- [15] Starkie, Babara, (2013) "[Data sharing through parent portals: An exploration of parental motivation, data use, and the promise of prolonged parental involvement.](#)" Harvard Family Research Project.
- [16] Gallagher, Lawrence, Barbara Means, & Christine Padilla (2008), "[Teachers' Use of Student Data Systems to Improve Instruction: 2005 to 2007.](#)" US Department of Education.
- [17] Brunner, Cornelia, Chad Fasca, Juliette Heinze, Margaret Honey, Daniel Light, Ellen Mardinach, & Dara Wexler. "Linking data and learning: The Grow Network study (2005)," Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk Vol. 10, No, 3 pp241-267.
- [18] Kaya, Ergün, & Murat Azaltun(2012), "[Role of information systems in supply chain management and its application on five-star hotels in Istanbul.](#)" Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology Vol. 3, No. 2, pp138-146.
- [19] Mandinach, Ellen B, (2012), "[A perfect time for data use: Using data-driven decision making to inform practice.](#)" Educational Psychologist Vol. 47, No. 2, pp71-85.
- [20] Datnow, Amanda, Vicki Park, and Priscilla Wohlstetter, (2007), "[Achieving with data.](#)" Los Angeles: University of Southern California, Center on Educational Governance (2007).

USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION, BUT AT WHAT COST?

Avanti P. Sethi and Ramesh Subramoniam

University of Texas at Dallas, USA

ABSTRACT

Use of technology in the field of education has been a blessing. Faster grading, quicker notes / media availability for students, interactive communication outside of classrooms with students and faculty, online courses etc. have added to the enhancement of our education system. But when technology is pushed in teaching without proper thought, it becomes a black box approach at the cost of intuition, commonsense, and overall understanding of the concepts. Instead of supplementing technology in the process of learning, it has been used in making the black box approach more common. When we can shift the question from “How to educate with technology?” to “How to teach people best, and how should we design learning experiences in light of existing technology?”, then learning becomes a way to quench curiosity, and passion for learning will become a never ending pursuit for students. Models and textbook theories can help build the knowledge base, but they miss the context [5,7]. Students take them at face value without thinking through the real world implications. This is a recipe for failure since the industry expects business school students to tell the story with a strong reference to the context. A simplistic understanding of the formulas is what students’ need instead of a plug and solve formula based teaching method.

KEYWORDS

MS Excel, Break-even Analysis, Probability Distribution, Lines and circles

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijite/V8N1/8119ijite02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijite/vol8.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Stevenson, Operations Management, McGraw Hill Education, 2018, 13th edition, ISBN 978-1-259-66747-3
- [2] Keller, Gerald, Statistics for Management and Economics, Cengage Publishing, 10th Edition, ISBN10: 1285425456
- [3] Sethi, Avanti, "[Use of Excel in Statistics: Problem Solving vs Problem Understanding](#)" International Journal on Integrating Technology in Education, Vol. 4, No. 4, December 2015
- [4] Peck, Kyle L. and Dorricott, Denise, "[Why Use Technology?](#)", 11-14, Vol. 51, April 1994.
- [5] Carlson, Ben, "9 Things they don't teach you in business school", Business Insider, October 2015.
- [6] Rachael Law Schuetz, Gina Biancarosa & Joanna Goode (2018) Is Technology the Answer? Investigating Students' Engagement in Math, Journal of Research on Technology in Education, 50:4, 318-332, DOI: 10.1080/15391523.2018.1490937
- [7] Subhash C. Mehta PhD, Sanjay S. Mehta PhD & Beh Lip Aun MBA (1999) The Evaluation of Business Text Books: An International Perspective, Journal of Professional Services Marketing, 19:2, 141-149, DOI: 10.1300/J090v19n02_09
- [8] Jorge A. Gaytan & John R. Slate (2002) Multimedia and the College of Business, Journal of Research on Technology in Education, 35:2, 186-205, DOI: 10.1080/15391523.2002.10782379